

An Inspirational Women for Today's World

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Abstract

There are many names in history who have proved that a women's strength is immeasurable, ones she makes her mind to make her journey a successful one, no one force can stop her! After reading the story of Rubini Selvanathan will get to understand that any woman can contribute to the society with her vigour irrespective of the circumstances. No matter what field or environment a woman belongs to. Read this article meditatively on an Inspirational Women for today's world and do something extraordinary which can help change the face of the society in a sanguine way.

Introduction

The changing time has now been changing women who had till of late been in bondage, into record breaker in all fields of human life opportunities and favourable circumstance come their way to enable them to build up a proper stage to create new records. They keep growing individualistic in striving single – handedly in their attempt to live their lives independently. Those of women who have started striving to end up victorious pave their ways themselves. When the final achievement of their aims starts appearing before them, they keep handling towards it overcoming all the hurdles on the way like boats that pierce through the waves.

Those of women who have set their eyes on some achievements are not fearful of battled fields. They never waver on their march on seeing great hurdles. They have great confidence in them to win at the last. Dr.Rubini Selvanathan is one such woman and she has been living a full life after having achieved her aims through her confident striving.

The Daughter of Point Pedro

Sri Lanka is an island in the southern hemisphere of the great globe. Till of late it looked like a beautiful and bounteous world in mind-set of some iron people. This enchanting island has lost its beauty and peace and now looks like a dead silent cemetery.

This sad history has soaked countless peoples lives in blood, it has changed the course of many people life. Rubini Selvanathan is one such person. He full life in her father country Germany and the name and fame that she has earned there odd glory to women as a whole.

She had been born as the daughter of Guna Nayagam – Ganamari Couple of Paruthithurai in Sri Lanka. Her father, Guna Nayagam, had been a teacher at Hartley college. Rubini had been good at singing even as a child while she was at school, no competition, be it in drama, music, elocution are even in any event of sports or games was held without her participation. After having completed her school education in her home country. She continued her higher studies in India. She returned to Sri Lanka in 1974.

The Sri Lanka Radio had a Christian programme in its Asian Service called Tree Gospel she joined this service as its singer and voice lender. In recognition of her talents they appointed her the Editor of the publication named, Tree Gospel. They entrusted her with the translation of books in English into Tamil. On accepting this task, she translated the book, back to the Bible.

Married Life

The Married Life that changed her life. When Rubini grew into a noble young woman and got married to Thiru Vinasithambi Selvanatha, the well known industrialist of point Pedro and the proprietor of Lakshmi Motor company in 1978. Their married life began well and went on happily for a while. Unfortunately disquieting developments began befalling the Sri Lankan Society. At last the young couple fled their country in 1985 and landed in Germany. The rich and beautiful Germany gave them asylum.

Pursuit of Arts in Germany

Germany provided the couple with new experiences. Rubini wanted to pursue an art in that country. As she had desired. She got an opportunity to work in the German TV. She did not get as much Co-Operation and encouragement as she had yearned for. But she did not give herself to despondency. She continued to work with self confidence and hope, and slowly started getting recognition to her talents.

Tom Cason, a producer of programmes in English, appreciated her talents in 1990 assigned the production of his 30 minute programme to her. After a while she produced three short films in English and released them in Berlin, the capital of Germany. She teaches English to boys and girls of Tamil origin living in Germany, to find admission to Trinity College she is the representative for Trinity College London. Prepare more than 100 students for the English Language.

The Influence of the Sari on the Western World

Europeans in general have a great respect for the culture and his life style of Tamils. They love to see Tamil women in their traditions sari. They keep wondering at the saris artistic nature and the beautiful way in which Tamil Women wear it.

She has been attending world film festivals as a film journalist. As soon as the organizers see her in her sari they give her extra attention and make things comfortable for her. Some times they go the extent of arranging a special felicitation of her sari once one of her colleagues desired to wear a sari, but did not know how to wear it so Rubini herself helped in her rapture.

Work and Appreciation

In addition to working as a teacher, she has been running school. She has been offering a crash course in English language to help those who seek admission to university of London None of the Europeans in the classroom took her for a teacher. They thought that she was a student.

‘Europeans do not take us as efficient and clever individuals easily. They put to me so many questions to ascertain my scholarship. She reminisces. On her part she remained calm and composed and answered their questions very clearly and convincingly. The students of older age group usually attend classes in evening and those of younger age groups in forenoon. Usually American, Australians or Britons were chosen as teachers to Coach.

However, her first name, Gloriana, her great command over English, had acted as a helping hand. Nearly 100 students are guided and trained by her from the London Examination.

Every year Oscar Prize is given to the best motion picture and the best actors and actresses. They Hollywood actors Kevin Spacy and Rusell Crowe, were given Oscar Prize of 2002 and Nickol Kidmann were slected for prices in 2004.

Conclusion

Rubini still keeps growing up whetting up her self-confidence and leaves the stamp of her personality and genius every piece of work that she later up. Her versatile life has been serving as an instrument to Empower weak women. She stands as a model for the Enterprising Woman. She created a history of her own to be emulted by the members of her younger generation.

References

- Karen O'Connor, (2010). Gender and Women's Leadership: A Reference Handbook, Publisher: SAGE Publications, Indian pvt itd Chennai.
- Kavitha Albert, (2007). Sweat and Success part-1, Jeba Malini publication: Kanyakumari.
- Duflo E. (2011), Women's Empowerment and Economic Development, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge
- Goswami, L. (2013). Education for Women Empowerment. ABHIBYAKTI: Annual Journal, 1, 17-18.